

The Relationship Between Unlimited Improvement And Business Performance

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to investigate the relationship between performance and unlimited improvement among employees of The Libyan Iron and Steel Company. The population of all the employees of General Administration of The Libyan Iron and Steel Company in 2018 was 500 people who the population of the whole number of all people were selected as a sample due to limitation. Of the 44 questionnaires that were distributed among employees, 40 usable questionnaires were obtained that the same number as the sample was taken in consideration. To collect the data, the questionnaire of the performance management (Shahcheraghi, 2001), standard questionnaire of unlimited improvement (realized) were used. Pearson correlation coefficient was used to analyze the data. The results indicate that there is a significant positive relationship between performance management and unlimited improvement and its components (planning, standardizing, and improving the quality of work, relationship with customer, human resources development and maintenance policy.

Keywords: Performance Management, unlimited Improvement, Employees of General Administration of The Libyan Iron and Steel Company.

I. Introduction

Industrial society is progressing and enters the era of information and communication. Therefore, we should always find solutions of character and more profitable for product and services, in recent competitive world, the cost of delaying in implementing administrative procedures modified is not less than the cost of delay using the latest technologies. Today, titles such as a successful, long-lasting, idealistic, left, excellent, perfect, sublime etc., organization are the common expressions of field of organization and management study and different groups of people are looking to identify features such organizations (Küçük, 2011) .

The organizations with superior performance is an organization that obtains better results to par organizations in a long-term period of a coherent management structure and ability to adapt appropriately to the changes targeted key feature of unlimited improvement and proper treatment of employees as the main asset (Isakhani, 2008), since the operating system will come into force by humans.

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So it can be rightly argued that the most important organizations asset is the same human resources. Attention to human resources in organizations in recent years dedicated a large part of the time and capital of organizations ahead to individual. Now, smart managers know that however they invest in the context of development and promotion of human resources they have ensured success, efficiency and competitive advantage of the organization (Jazani, 1999). Unlimited improvement of organizational performance creates great resource of synergy that these resources can support growth planning, developing and creating opportunities for business excellence. Governments, organizations and institutions always seek to achieve this objective.

Without studying and awareness of the progress and achievement of objectives and without identifying the challenges facing the organization and gain feedback and information on the implementation of policies formulated and identifying areas that need serious improvement, unlimited improvement of performance will be achieved (Anderson & Jakesz, 2008).

According to kaizen who definition of that change is or the better or unlimited improvement and gradual, management functions are divided into two main categories that they mean to create improvement and keep improvement. Based on this view, the intention of the director is not only the one alleged in the position of organizational management, but anyone who has the responsibility to do something, is assumed a director or in other words managing the work. Therefore, we can say that all employees are managers or controlling at least one activity (Küçük vd., 2015)

This view is led to obviating a split in the traditional attitude between managers and employees and it is a great motivation for all employees and this is the motivation that all are enforced to think as process owners to improve the process and its constituents (Küçük, 2011). Therefore, the aim of the study was to investigate the relationship between performance management and unlimited improvement among employees of General Administration of The Libyan Iron and Steel Company.

II. Aims of Study, Scope and Methodology

The aims of the study is to investigation the relationship between unlimited improvement and business performance management.

The scope of study was in employees of The Libyan Iron and Steel Company , to test a scale developed in this subject with the research to be carried out and the subject in practice In addition 60 questionnaires were distributed, while 20

were not answered and I received 40 questionnaires from the company employees in The Libyan Iron and Steel Company .

Unlimited improvement has been development by Küçük (2011). Küçük (2011) and (2012) scale have been used for unlimit improvement variable.

Business performance scale Küçük, O. &Kocaman G. (2014) these scale are likert scale 5 agree this agree

III. Research Model and Hypothesis

The process is the process of obtaining a value by a series of activities connected to each other. They enter the left side of the procession, putting the incremental value on the right. This value is in the form of a product, service or information that meets customer expectations and requirements. Everything done in business is almost a process (Küçük & Polat, 2013).

The model of the study is shown in Figure (1)

Figure 1. Model of Study

As seen in Figure 1. Have been registered that relationship between unlimited improvement and business performance.

Küçük (2011) and (2012), Ay and Nurov (2017) determined that there is a relationship between unlimited improvement and organizational performance.

so our hypothesis registered that

H1: There is relationship between unlimited improvement and business performance.

IV. Data Analysis

The Table 1. shows that factor analysis of the relationship between performance and unlimited improvement among employees of The Libyan Iron and Steel Compan

Table 1. Factor Analysis of Unlimited Improvement

Unlimited improvement	Factor Load	Core value	Variance Explanatio (%)n Rate	Cronbach Alfa	Average	KMO value
1. There are unchanged person vehicle applications or processes that are excluded	,840	3,190	23,199 19,152	,850	2,20	,644
2.Unlimited recovery (improvement of whole process, application, person, machine equipment and supplier) is important	,674	2,99			2,12	
3. Too administrators participate in the training	,671				2,20	
4. Time managers are included in the improvement	,663				1,88	
5. The organizational structure as a whole is included in the improvement	607				2,18	
6. The occupations are included in the improvement	609				2,23	
7. The tools are included in the improvement	590				1,99	
8. Time processes are included in the improvement	814				2,17	
9. Total applications are included in the improvement	,777		25,730		1,89	
10. Time suppliers are included in the improvement	,668				2,15	
11.Managers can be changed	592				2,24	
12.The organizational structure is changeable	767				2,13	

13.The occupations can be changed	812			1,98
14.Tool tools can be changed	599			1,90
15.The processes can be changed	612			2,22
16.Total applications are changeable	810			2,25
17.Time suppliers can be changed	689			2,15
18.Mesh times can be changed	599			2,11
19.Reservation rights can be changed	787			1,89

As shown in Table 1 and Table 2, the value of Kaiser-MeyerOlkin (KMO) was found to be 0.572. Since this value is over 0.4 or even 0.5, it is shown that sampling is sufficient and meaningful factors can be obtained from research data. The fact that all expressions have a factor load greater than 0.5 and an eigenvalue greater than 1 indicate that the expressions are suitable for use in analysis. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.878. Since this value is greater than 0.80, the scale is highly reliable and the variance explanation rate is 67,642%. Thus, it was decided that the scale could be used in scientific research.

Table 2. Factor Analysis of Business Performance.

Business Performance	Factor Load	Core value	Variance Explanation (%) Rate	Cronbach Alfa	Average	KMO value
1. Level of satisfaction of our suppliers	800	3,176	24,123	,879	2,11	,680
2.The establishment of new product / service development success It has.	780				1,80	
3.The reputation and image of our establishment is high.	808				2,22	
4. Our business has a high market share.	690				1,88	
5 The quality of our new product / service is high.	599				2,15	
6.The productivity of our business is high.	812				2,11	
7. The level of reaching our business goals is high.	871				1,85	
8. Our business has high sales.	610				2,12	
9. The profitability of our business is high.	813				2,22	
10. Customer satisfaction is high.	597				1,90	

According to the consequences of the research, since the importance level of most of the scales included in the scale is between 3.67 and 5.00, it has been evaluated that the expressions in the measure are mostly accepted by the participants.

According to the results of the Cronbach Alpha test conducted to measure the reliability of the research conducted to determine the effect of unlimited improvement on business performance, (0,850) .

Conferring to these values, customer satisfaction (0,830), development new product (0,780), market share (0,690). quality of new product (0,599), productivity of business (0,812), reaching of goals (0,871), Customer satisfaction (0,597), which are sub-dimensions of business performance, was not evaluated because the number of questions of performance was good , indicating that the scale is highly reliable(Küçük, 2016: 228-231; Kalaycı, 2010: 405).

Table 3. shows the relationship between unlimited improvement and performance.

Table 3. Correlation Analysis between unlimited improvement and performance

unlimited improvement	Performance	unlimited improvement
	0.77	1
	.00	.00
Business performance	1	0.77
	.00	.00

According to correlation analysis there is the strongly relationship between unlimited improvement and performance. Where, it was (77%) (Küçük, 2016.) if (0.6) , (0.8) Based on this result, strongly relationship so there is strongly relationship the alternative hypothesis "There is relationship between unlimited improvement and performance" is accepted.

V. Discussion

This paper has considered both quality improvement and productivity improvement as being related but distinct approaches to unlimited improvement. TQM and six sigma have been considered as typical quality improvement strategies and lean thinking and the TOC as productivity improvement strategies (O. Küçük, 2011), (Antony & Banuelas, 2002) .Within the organization devices, it is noted that the quality standards, such as ISO13485:2003 emphasis unlimited improvement when compared with the general ISO9001 standards, suggesting that unlimited improvement can be problematic in the context of regulatory processes (O. Küçük et al., 2015).

In comparing the applications of the strategies discussed, two distinct emphases are observed. One focuses on a discrete process approach using structured programmers (Petersen, 2003). The other focuses on creating an organizational culture that directs the efforts of employees. In this regard, six sigma and the TOC are largely process focused, while TQM and lean thinking are largely culturally focused. While it is noted that this categorisation is a somewhat simplified view of how these strategies are implemented in real world situations, the ethos of the strategies can be clearly seen. When choosing to implement a strategy for unlimited improvement, leadership is critical to success. The situational leadership model has been adapted and can be used to indicate whether a cultural or process focused approach might be more appropriate in different situations (Francisco & Boake, 2003). This approach considers how “empowered” a workforce is and how the expertise is distributed within an organization in order to determine what style of leadership is most appropriate and therefore which unlimited improvement strategies might work better. It is suggested that organizations where the expertise is centralized and where a more directive leadership is used will find process focused strategies easier to implement, while organizations where expertise is distributed and leadership is more supportive will find cultural strategies more appropriate (O. Küçük, 2012).

A review of the organization’s development level and the preferred leadership style of management will help the organization to choose a strategy that requires a minimum from the current state of the organization onto the path of unlimited improvement. Research indicates that, whereas larger companies within the medical devices sector do apply unlimited improvement methods, many of the small and medium size..

VI. Results And Suggestions

In the light of these conclusions, the following suggestions can be made for labor management and institutional managers. TQM and six sigma have been considered as typical quality improvement strategies and lean thinking and the TOC as productivity improvement strategies.

- * Create an organizational culture that directs employees' efforts towards unlimited improvement and increased productivity .
- * Consider TQM and Six Sigma as model strategies for quality improvement.
- * Organizations must adopt a strategy for unlimited improvement .
- * Leadership is critical to success.

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